

11th INTERNATIONAL CERAMIDE CONFERENCE

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Holding a virtual ICC came with a few challenges, not least of which was having a more limited time to allow researchers to present their work. This became even harder when we received an unprecedented number of abstracts!

The scientific committee did their best to select talks from diverse areas and from presenter across the globe. As always in the ICC series, we have also aimed to give junior investigators – students and postdocs – the opportunities to present their work on the international stage.

However, realizing that the pandemic has severely hit the field and reduced the chances of labs presenting their most recent findings, we made the decision – with the authors permission – to send out all the abstracts we received to attendees.

We hope that this will give new insight and spur new collaborations in the field

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ABSTRACT
BOOK

Metachromatic Leukodystrophy – Late Infantile Type

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Metachromatic leukodystrophy is a rare lysosomal storage disease caused by mutations in the ARSA gene at the locus 22q13.33 and PSAP gene at the locus 10q22. Mutations in ARSA gene result in deficiencies of enzyme arylsulfatase A. This enzyme normally functions within lysosomes, degrading newly synthesized cerebroside-3-sulfate into cerebroside and sulfate. Accumulation of cerebroside-3-sulfate in lysosomes lead to progressive demyelination of white matter throughout the central and peripheral nervous system and lead to progressive motor and cognitive deterioration. The severity of clinical manifestations depends on the residual ARSA activity. Detection of mutation could provide further knowledge about genotype-phenotype correlations. There is no specific treatment for Metachromatic Leukodystrophy. Gene therapy is future treatment potential. In late-infantile form of Metachromatic leukodystrophy (50–60 % of all cases) there are clinical manifestations in the first 3 years of life. Often the first signs of late-infantile form include difficulty walking caused by progressive demyelination of the peripheral nervous system and lose ability to speak. Further progression of disease includes blindness, loss of walking and unresponsiveness. During 2017-2020 in Service for Medical Genetics in Vojvodina, there were two children (brother and sister) who suffer from Metachromatic leukodystrophy. Diagnosis was established according clinical deterioration and tigroid pattern of the white matter on MRI of endocranium. Mutation analysis of the arylsulfatase A gene (ARSA) encoding enzyme arylsulfatase A revealed a compound heterozygosity. Also, during the same period our team provided prenatal diagnosis for next pregnancies of their non-consanguineous parents.